

Developing students' speech in English classes

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Abstract: In today's era of globalization, English has become one of the most widely used languages in the world. English is widely used not only in international relations, but also in the fields of education, science, business and technology. Therefore, learning English is important for every young generation. This article also provides additional information and opinions on this topic.

Key words: speech, language richness, research, activity, communication, development, goal...

Currently, the main goal in the educational process is to teach students to be able to communicate fully and effectively in English. This is done by increasing their vocabulary and developing free speech. This article talks about the importance, methods and methods of developing students' speech in English classes. It is worth noting that the role of learning English in the modern education system is very large. Through this language, students not only get acquainted with foreign literature, scientific articles and technologies, but also acquire communication skills necessary for success in their future professional activities. In particular, English is the main tool for working with world universities, international organizations and corporations. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the development of students' language skills, especially their speech, during English lessons.

The need to develop students' speech One of the most important goals in learning English is to teach students to communicate freely and effectively in this language.

Speaking skills enable students to express their thoughts clearly, fluently and comprehensibly. However, many students struggle with speaking because the lessons focus more on grammar and writing. Therefore, not only teaching grammar, but also speech development

should be prioritized in English language classes. It is also necessary to take into account some basic principles in the development of students' speech:

1. Practical approach - in addition to the theoretical study of the language, students should also apply it in practice. This is done by actively participating in communication processes, talking, participating in discussions.

2. Creating an atmosphere of free communication - a positive atmosphere should be

created in classes so that students can freely express their thoughts. They should not be afraid of mistakes in language learning and develop their language skills.

3. Interesting topics - if lessons are organized based on topics that match the interests of students, they will be more interested in communicating in English and actively participate in this process.

4. Using active means of communication - through audio, video materials, conversations, role-plays and other communicative methods, students can enrich and develop their

English speech.

The following can be cited as methods of speech development:

1. Role-plays and dramas: Role-plays and drama methods are one of the most effective tools for developing students' speech. Through this method, students learn to use the language in a way that is appropriate to life situations and improve their communication skills. For example, through situations such as shopping in a store, talking in a hotel or airport, students practice their speech. Through drama, students imagine themselves in the place of other people, learn to express their thoughts and react to certain situations.

2. Discussions and conversations. Discussions and conversations help to express students' thoughts more broadly and more clearly. By organizing discussions and conversations in English classes, students learn to express their opinions on various topics, defend their points of view, and listen to others' opinions. Through this method, they learn different levels of complexity of the language, new words and expressions.

3. Use of audiovisual means. In this regard, audiovisual materials are of great importance in the development of students' speech. Through films, series, interviews, radio broadcasts,

students not only improve their listening skills, but also improve their speaking in the process. Teachers can use such materials to discuss topics with students or analyze them together.

4. Work with feathers (pair). Language acquisition can be accelerated by putting students into pairs and encouraging them to communicate together. Each pair asks each other questions, shares ideas and learns new words through interaction. Through this method, students develop language skills by listening to each other.

In addition, increasing motivation in English language classes is also considered effective. It is important to increase motivation in classes for the development of students' speech. Teachers should show students interesting aspects of language learning and involve them in active communication. At the same time, it is

possible to increase students' interest in language learning by encouraging them in relation to their achievements. For example, students who have achieved good results should be given small gifts or encouraging words to increase their self-confidence. Assessing students' English speaking is also an important process. Teachers should monitor students' speech and analyze their level of development. For this, special assessment criteria should be developed, for example: pronunciation, grammatical correctness, vocabulary, fluency and clear expression of communication. Also, showing students mistakes in their speech and helping them to correct them will increase the effectiveness of the lesson. Interactive methods also ensure the active participation of students and play an important role in the development of their language skills.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that today interactive technologies, including online platforms, mobile applications and other digital tools, form the basis of developing students' speech in English classes.

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